

A New Synthesis of 3:10-Dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine.

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3:10-Dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine (V), which had previously been prepared by one of us (Chakravarti and Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 196) has now been synthesised by a method similar to that used for the synthesis of 3:11-dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine (Chakravarti, Haworth and Perkin, *ibid.*, 1927, 2265). β -*m*-Methoxyphenylethylamine, prepared by a slight modification of the method previously described (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2269) was condensed with *p*-methoxyphenylacetic acid (prepared by a modification of the method of Mauthner, *Annalen*, 1909, 370, 374; Wakeman and Dakin, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1911, 9, 150; Cain, Simonsen and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 1036) and *p*-methoxyphenylaceto- β -*m*-methoxyphenylethylamide (I) (m.p. 81°) was converted in a yield of more than 80% into 6-methoxy-1(4'-methoxybenzyl)-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (II). The base readily forms a hydrochloride and a picrate and oxidises rapidly on exposure to air and is readily

reduced by zinc and sulphuric acid to 6-methoxy-1(4'-methoxybenzyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (III), a base yielding a crystalline sulphate and picrate. Attempts to convert (III) into 3:10-dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine by means of formaldehyde were unsuccessful, invariably gummy products being obtained. It was ultimately found that treatment of the *N*-formyl derivative of (III) with phosphorus oxychloride gave 3:10-dimethoxydihydroprotoberberine (IV)

in 20% yield. The substitution of phosphorus pentoxide for the oxychloride did not effect any improvement in the yield. The base (IV) was not isolated as such, except in a preliminary experiment, but directly reduced by zinc dust and hydrochloric acid to 3:10 dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine (V), m.p. 139°. A mixed melting point with a specimen synthesised by the

previous method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 201) caused no depression.

The interesting point which arises from this investigation is that whilst the first cyclisation, that is to say, the conversion of (I) into (II) takes place readily, the second cyclisation, *i.e.*, the conversion of (III) into (IV) takes place with much less readiness. This is undoubtedly due to the presence of a *para* activating methoxy group in (I), and the absence of such a group in (III).

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Methoxyphenylaceto-*m*-methoxyphenylethylamide, (I).—*β*-*m*-Methoxyphenylethylamine was prepared by a slight modification of our previous method (*loc. cit.*), the modification consisting in methylating *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde by shaking it with slight excess of dimethyl sulphate in alkaline solution and then heating the product for 1 hour on the water-bath. Thus the use of methyl alcohol was

obtained and a 90 per cent. yield of *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde was obtained.

In preparing *p*-methoxyphenylacetic acid the following modification was used:

The azlactone obtained by the condensation of anisaldehyde and hippuric acid was hydrolysed by means of 10 p. c. sodium hydroxide solution, and the alkaline solution was then saturated with sulphur dioxide, the benzoic acid collected, and the filtrate acidified and boiled. *p*-Methoxyphenylpyruvic acid which gradually separated was collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. This acid (m.p. 192°) was oxidised in cold alkaline solution with hydrogen peroxide. On acidifying the solution, *p*-methoxyphenylacetic acid, m.p. 86°, separated in beautiful plates and in an excellent yield.

Equivalent quantities of β -*m*-methoxyphenylethylamine and *p*-methoxyphenylacetic acid were heated at 180° for 2 hours. On crystallising the product from benzene through the aid of animal charcoal, *p*-methoxyphenylaceto- β -*m*-methoxyphenylethylamide (I) was obtained as colourless plates, m.p. 81°, in a good yield. (Found: C, 72.0; H, 7.2. $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$ requires C, 72.2; H, 7.0 per cent.).

6-Methoxy-1(4'-methoxybenzyl)-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline, (II).—The amide (I) (10 g.) was heated with phosphorus oxychloride (25 c.c.) for 2 hours on the steam-bath and then kept overnight. The mixture was decomposed with cold water and the clear solution thus obtained was basified with sodium hydroxide in presence of benzene in a separating funnel, the precipitate formed being immediately shaken up with benzene. The alkaline solution was once more extracted with benzene and part of the combined benzene extract (A) was dried over potassium carbonate, and concentrated to a small bulk when a colourless oil was obtained.

A crystalline hydrochloride and a crystalline picrate, m.p. 146° (Found: C, 56.3; H, 4.6. $C_{24}H_{22}O_3N_4$ requires C, 56.5; H, 4.3 per cent) was prepared from the above base by usual methods.

6-Methoxy-1(4'-methoxybenzyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroxyisoquinoline, (III) was obtained by extracting the benzene extract (A) with dilute sulphuric acid, and reducing the acid solution with zinc dust. On cooling, the crystalline sulphate was deposited in the form of plates. The sulphate was dissolved in water and decomposed with ammonia, and the tetrahydro base extracted with chloroform, dried over potassium carbonate and the solvent removed, leaving the base as an oil. The hydrochloride, obtained by dissolving the oil in hot

dilute hydrochloric acid, and cooling, separated as a crystalline powder, m.p. 196°. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 7.1. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2NCl$ requires C, 67.6; H, 6.9 per cent.). The *picrate* prepared in alcoholic solution is sparingly soluble in cold alcohol and separated from this solvent as a crystalline powder, m.p. 192° (decomp.).

3:10-Dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine, (V).—This base could not be obtained by treating the foregoing base with formaldehyde in the usual manner. This base was obtained in a 20 per cent. yield by the following method. The base (III) was heated with equivalent amount of anhydrous formic acid in an oil-bath at 200–10° until effervescence had ceased (3 hours). The product was dissolved in toluene and boiled with phosphorus oxychloride for 1½ hours. After remaining overnight light petroleum was added and the clear liquid decanted from the dark coloured gum, the latter extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid (charcoal), and the solution of dihydroprotoberberine reduced by heating with excess of zinc dust for 2 hours, during which the yellow solution became colourless. The hot liquid was filtered, the filtrate decomposed with ammonia, the base extracted with chloroform, dried over potassium carbonate, the chloroform removed, and the residue crystallised from methyl alcohol. On recrystallisation from methyl alcohol with the aid of animal charcoal, the substance was obtained in beautiful prisms, m.p. 139°. (Found: C, 77.1; H, 7.3. $C_{19}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 77.3; H, 7.1 per cent.).

In a preliminary experiment, an attempt was made first to get 3:10-dimethoxydihydroprotoberberine (IV) in a crystalline state and then to reduce it to (V). It was found, however, that 3:10-dimethoxydihydroprotoberberine (IV), crystallised much less readily than 3:10-dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine (V).